

Fairness, justice, and equity in research integrity guidelines across the world: A critical discourse analysis

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Abstract

Currently, Research Integrity (RI) initiatives are predominantly shaped by countries in the Global North (GN). Given the influence of GN funders and publishers on global research practices, RI standards set in the GN are frequently also applied in the Global South (GS). While the GS is increasingly involved in RI initiatives there still exist a risk of ethical imperialism, where GN ethical standards are imposed as universal. This study examines if and how ethical imperialism manifests in regulatory RI documents by assessing their treatment of research fairness using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). We conducted a scoping review to collect regional, national and international RI guidelines and codes of conduct. Conducting a search of grey literature and scientific literature, we included up to 65 codes that explicitly refer to responsible conduct of research or research integrity directed at researchers. Our analysis employs CDA to assess how fairness is constructed in these documents and analyze implicit and explicit power dynamics, silences, and assumptions. Our sample includes an uneven representation of countries: RI codes come mostly from European countries, with limited representation from Africa and Latin America. Only a few documents explicitly mention issues of injustice, such as knowledge and material extractivism, epistemic injustice, and socioeconomic inequities and precariousness. Few codes explicitly confront colonial hierarchies, but those that do tend to come from formerly colonized nations. Some documents acknowledge non-Western knowledge systems and alternative ethical frameworks, yet many still reflect hierarchies in their language, for instance, portraying indigenous and marginalized groups as passive agents and receivers of research rather than as groups capable of conducting research. While some RI codes integrate diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) principles, their depth varies. Some documents employ "diversity" as an empty concept, while others propose concrete measures to counter discrimination and systemic inequalities. Finally, fairness is frequently reduced to procedural mechanisms, such as fair authorship, peer review, and misconduct investigations, which, while essential, risk treating fairness as bureaucratic compliance rather than a structural transformation of research. Overall, European RI frameworks tend to emphasize fairness without justice, reinforcing procedural rather than structural visions of fairness.

Introduction

Research integrity (RI) can be understood as engaging in research behaviors that are in line with high methodological and professional standards (Boehme et al., 2016). RI is recognized as crucial to safeguard the trustworthiness of research, ensure high research quality, and produce valid and relevant results. Across the globe, there are a growing number of initiatives to foster RI, such as the development of normative guidance, support structures (e.g. confidential counselors), and training (Mejlgaard et al., 2020). Normative RI guidance, in the form of guidelines, policy statements, standard operating procedures, and codes of conduct, play an important role by explicating the principles and practices considered to contribute to good research practice within specific research communities (Hastings et al., 2022). These guidance documents often differ in target and scope: they can be international (Resnik & Shamoo, 2011), national (Knaw et al., 2018) or institutional (Aubert Bonn et al., 2017), and can be general or disciplinary specific (Hastings et al., 2022; Ščepanović et al., 2021).

Understandings of RI in these documents have been greatly influenced by serious cases of research misconduct and the so called 'replication crisis' in empirical and mostly quantitative research fields, where many published results cannot be reproduced (Camerer et al., 2016; Ioannidis, 2012; Klein et al., 2018). This has led to certain topics traditionally being considered as core to RI, namely i) misconduct, both in terms of prevention and handling; ii) addressing replication-related biases and poor research practices; and iii) fair authorship practices. However, as understandings of influences on good and bad research conduct develop, other topics are increasingly recognized as important such as research culture and supervision (Geller, 2010; Muthanna & Alduais, 2021).

One of the 'newer' topics addressed by RI initiatives concerns diversity, fairness, equity, inclusion and justice, which we collectively refer to from now on as 'research fairness' (beyond the narrow scope of fair authorship practices). The recent Cape Town Statement on Fostering Research Integrity through Fairness and Equity (Horn et al., 2023), launched at the 7th World Conference on Research Integrity 2022, recognized inequitable research practices as undermining the integrity of research and made recommendations to improve equitable research practices in collaborations between high-income and low- and middle-income countries. There is, however, still much discussion among RI experts about the relationship between research fairness and RI. Some experts see research fairness as a core issue for RI, especially in international collaborations, as reflected in the Cape Town Statement, while others see it as an unrelated topic or a human resources concern (Moher et al., 2020), constituting a type of 'mission creep' in RI initiatives.

Labib (2025) argues that despite these apparent differences in perspectives, most dominant approaches to RI - even including initiatives such as the Cape Town Statement or the TRUST Code - A Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships (TRUST, 2018) - do not actually address research fairness seriously. This is because whilst these initiatives might promote diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI), they usually neglect to acknowledge or address the ongoing coloniality of research. This coloniality involves research being often used as an instrument of imperialist goals and enduring colonial structures in research, thereby contributing towards physical and epistemic injustices in the world. Labib further argues that most dominant RI initiatives prioritize research concerns relevant for Global North (GN)¹, a bias stemming from the GN origin of most of these initiatives.

¹ We use the terms Eurocentric and Global North as interchangeable to refer to those regions which are historically tied to colonial power (European countries and the European diaspora, including Canada, the USA, Australia, and other white settler-colonial states) and Global South to refer to those that have historically been subjected to colonial domination. We recognize that these terms are inherently reductionist, risk reinforcing binary divisions, and overlook the diversity and heterogeneity within and

While most dominant RI initiatives can be considered Eurocentric, they have global influence, for instance via funding frameworks, publishing ethics, and data management requirements. Therefore, they constitute a form of ‘ethical imperialism’, in which Eurocentric understandings of RI and responsible conduct of research are imposed across the world (Israel, 2018; Labib, 2025). This can reinforce and compound existing colonial hierarchies and inequities in research and negatively impact research fairness. For instance, Dutta et al. (2021) argue that the large focus on replication in current ethics and data management discussions is misguided. It is based on a GN positivist paradigm which sees research as instrumental towards obtaining ‘objective’ truth, ignoring or devaluing other knowledge production approaches based on situated, experiential knowledge, lived experiences, community, and embodiment. In this light, the authors argue that the replication crisis should be seen as the “epistemological limits to knowledge as science, situated in the colonizing ideology of the North”; in other words, as highlighting the limitations and problems of the positivist objective research paradigm. Instead, the focus of the research community to ‘fix’ the replication crisis by increasing reproducibility, ignores these core problems and reproduces the same limitations that are the cause of the crisis to begin with. This example highlights how current priorities in the field of RI can be considered as highly Eurocentric.

In recognition of this situation, we identify three main concerns of research fairness, which we now refer to as themes or ‘blocks’, that are relevant to discussions of RI. These are 1) fairness as addressing injustices, 2) fairness as attention to colonial hierarchies and 3) fairness as diversity, equity and inclusion. These are elaborated on further in Table 1.

Table 1: Themes concerning the relationship between fairness and RI

Themes/blocks	Description
<i>Fairness as Addressing Injustices</i>	Research fairness cannot exist without addressing actual injustices related to research (Labib, 2025). This includes material injustices (e.g. contribution of research to genocides and theft), as well as injustices that permeate knowledge systems themselves, referred to as ‘epistemic injustices’. Epistemic injustice refers to the devaluation and marginalization of certain groups’ knowledge, often manifesting as testimonial injustice (discrediting or undervaluing knowledge from particular sources) or hermeneutical injustice (failing to recognize alternative ways of knowing and not having the resources to make sense of some social groups experiences) (Fricker, 2007). In addition to neglecting justice and injustice, RI might contribute to these injustices directly by only valuing GN ethical paradigms (Lanzarotta, 2020).
<i>Fairness as Attention to Colonial Hierarchies</i>	Beyond addressing injustices, fairness has to do with challenging enduring hierarchies shaped by colonial logics. Institutions in GN countries are often assumed to be intellectual leaders in research. On the other hand, institutions in the rest of the world are often framed and treated as places for data extraction and application of policies and guidelines developed elsewhere (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2018; Tuhiwai Smith, 2012; Verges & Bohrer, 2021). This dynamic reinforces existing colonial hierarchies.
<i>Fairness as Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI)</i>	DEI can be understood in different ways. On the one hand, it can be understood as increasing the diversity of bodies and theories in research, and in defining what ‘good research’ is, requiring that all social groups – especially those marginalized or underrepresented – have a meaningful voice in defining good research

across regions, yet they are useful for highlighting the broad power asymmetries that continue to frame and shape research globally. Furthermore, the term Eurocentric allows us to explicitly recognize through language that these colonial global hierarchies come from European empires and the colonization of other parts of the world.

	practices and standards for all. Without DEI, RI initiatives reinforce existing inequities by privileging GN paradigms and priorities. On the other hand, DEI can also sometimes be seen as buzzwords that contribute to 'diversity ideology' where whites maintain their dominance in a multi-racial world by allowing for a diversity of bodies in certain spaces while maintaining racist, sexist and ableist power structures (Smith & Mayorga-Gallo, 2017)
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Considering these theoretical discussions, in this study we aim to assess how the relationship between RI and fairness is understood across the world, by analyzing national and international RI guidance documents. Our approach is theoretically informed and takes a critical, anti-colonial stance, guided by the 3 themes outlined in table 1. The goal is to expose tensions, hidden implications and inconsistencies in the guidance documents. At the same time, we also intend to test our theoretical understandings by finding materials that challenge, oppose or build on the three themes. More specifically, we have the following research questions:

1. What is the geographical distribution of these documents? This will help us to understand whether ethical imperialism can be empirically observable.
2. In what ways do these documents implicitly and explicitly address research fairness?

Methods

To address the research questions, we conducted a scoping review, and theoretically informed critical discourse analysis. We chose the latter approach to ensure that our analysis does not take the content of information in guidance documents at face value but rather scrutinize power structures, implicit meanings, and silences and omissions (Cummings et al., 2020). The methods used for this study have also been used in a parallel study focusing on open science (OS) (Crespo López et al., 2025)

2.1. Scoping review

We reported this scoping review in accordance with the [PRISMA-ScR guidance](#) to ensure methodological transparency and rigor. The review was designed to serve two studies: the present study on fairness in RI documents, and the parallel study on OS discourses (Crespo López et al., 2025). For this reason, our search strategy and inclusion criteria targeted national and international guidance documents for researchers, including codes of conduct, policy documents and guidelines that addressed either RI or OS. The inclusion of OS was therefore intentional, reflecting the dual design of the data collection. A comprehensive search was performed in the databases: Elsevier/Scopus and Clarivate Analytics/Web of Science Core Collection from inception to June 21, 2024 in collaboration with a medical information specialist (JCFK). The search included controlled and free text terms for synonyms of 'guideline' or 'standard' or 'policy' and 'research integrity' or 'ethical research' or 'open science'. The search was performed without restrictions for methodology, date or language. The full search strategies can be found in the Supplementary Materials. Duplicate articles were excluded by a medical information specialist (JCFK) using Endnote X20.0.1 (Clarivatetm).

- *Inclusion and exclusion criteria*

We focused on documents that apply to all research fields, rather than those addressing a specific disciplinary field. Additionally, only documents explicitly referring to RI or responsible conduct of research, and OS or open access were included. We also included documents about responsible data management, since they are often both related to RI and OS concerns, and documents about responsible collaboration since such documents often aim to more explicitly address issues of fairness and power differences among countries. However, we excluded documents on other subtopics within RI and OS.

In addition to documents which were national or international in scope, we also included documents related to research associated with a specific cultural or ethnic group, although we did not explicitly

search for these due to feasibility. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for documents to be included in the study can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Criteria related to	Inclusion	Exclusion
<i>Types of documents</i>	Guidelines, codes of conduct, policy statements, laws, regulations	Implementation guides or toolkits, research articles, opinion pieces, documents stating they are not regulatory documents
<i>Topic</i>	Explicit referral to: research integrity, open science, open access, responsible conduct of research, responsible data management Documents that provide guidance about good practices	Research ethics documents if they mostly focus on ethics review procedures or protection of research participants (human or animal); research integrity guidelines focused on a specific subtopic such as supervision, research culture, rewards and recognition, etc.; documents that only address research misconduct or misbehaviors
<i>Target group</i>	Researchers	Regulatory documents targeted specifically at institutions, journals, funders, publishers, policy makers, or other stakeholders
<i>Disciplinary focus</i>	Documents targeted at all disciplinary fields	Documents targeted at a specific disciplinary field or type of research (e.g. health research, quantitative studies, etc.)
<i>Date</i>	No date restrictions; in case of multiple versions of a document, use the latest version	None
<i>Language restrictions</i>	All languages	None
<i>Level of guidance</i>	National or international documents; documents targeted at specific cultural groups within or across countries	Documents targeted at specific research institutions
<i>Geographic focus</i>	All regions in the globe	None

- *Grey literature*

KL used Google (in incognito mode) to search for national RI and OS guidelines and codes of conduct per country mentioned in the UN member states (<https://www.un.org/en/about-us/member-states>) as well as Palestine and Taiwan, and continent (i.e. North Americ*, South Americ*/Latin Americ*, Afric*, Europ*, Asi*, Australi*). We used the following search terms to search for all documents across regions: ("research integrity" OR "responsible conduct of research" OR "ethics" OR "open science" OR "open data" OR "open access" OR "open code" OR "open infrastructure") AND ("code" OR "Code of conduct" OR "policy" OR "guideline" OR "standard" OR "best practice" OR "policies" OR "Statement"), and added the country or continent name to the search query to search for documents in a specific country or region.

When searching for documents in a specific country, KL searched within the Google domain of that country, if available.

In addition to the Google search, KL did a database search of the World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation, including the websites listed on the page on related websites (<https://www.wcrif.org/links>). The logbook of the gray literature search can be found in [supplementary information 1](#).

- *Published literature*

JCFK searched Scopus and Web of Science with the goal of finding published literature referring to documents that meet our inclusion criteria. The search terms used can be found in Table 3. The inclusion criteria for the published literature can be found in [supplementary information 2](#).

Table 3: Search terms for published literature

Database	Search terms
Scopus	TITLE ((guideline* OR standard* OR best-practice* OR policy OR policies OR (code* W/3 conduct*)) W/15 (research-integrit* OR (research* W/3 ethic*) OR (responsibl* W/3 (conduct* OR research)) OR open-research OR open-science OR open-data OR open-access OR open-code* OR open-infrastructure*)) OR AUTHKEY ((guideline* OR standard* OR best-practice* OR policy OR policies OR (code* W/3 conduct*)) W/15 (research-integrit* OR (research* W/3 ethic*) OR (responsibl* W/3 (conduct* OR research)) OR open-research OR open-science OR open-data OR open-access OR open-code* OR open-infrastructure*))
Web of Science	TI=((guideline* OR standard* OR best-practice* OR policy OR policies OR (code* NEAR/3 conduct*)) NEAR/15 (research-integrit* OR (research* NEAR/3 ethic*) OR (responsibl* NEAR/3 (conduct* OR research)) OR open-research OR open-science OR open-data OR open-access OR open-code* OR open-infrastructure*)) OR AK=((guideline* OR standard* OR best-practice* OR policy OR policies OR (code* NEAR/3 conduct*)) NEAR/15 (research-integrit* OR (research* NEAR/3 ethic*) OR (responsibl* NEAR/3 (conduct* OR research)) OR open-research OR open-science OR open-data OR open-access OR open-code* OR open-infrastructure*))

- *Contacting experts*

MCL identified national RI and OS experts and contacted them via email to inquire about relevant documents from their respective countries that met our inclusion criteria, particularly for countries where our gray and published literature search had not yielded results.

- *Screening*

The screening of published literature followed a two-stage process and was done using AI tool [rayyan.ai](#). First, titles and abstracts were independently screened by at least two researchers (MCL, CPP, KL, and a student intern, MH). Second, the full text of potentially relevant articles was reviewed by one author (MCL, CPP, or KL) and then double-checked by another, to confirm eligibility and to identify references to national or international RI and OS guidance documents that met our inclusion criteria.

For documents themselves (those extracted from the literature, found through gray literature searches, or identified by national experts), eligibility was first assessed by one author (MCL, CPP, or KL) and independently verified by another. Any discrepancies were discussed among the team until consensus was reached.

2.1.2 Data extraction

Of the included documents from the search, the RI documents were inputted into a data extraction table on Excel to record the following attributes: year, language, title, authors, national or international, country/region of origin and target country/region, to find in the [supplementary information 3](#). Any documents included that were not in English were translated using AI (ChatGPT or DeepSeek).

2.2. Descriptive analysis

We described the global coverage of national and international guidelines and codes of conduct for RI and OS.

2.3. Critical discourse analysis

We used MAXQDA to conduct a critical discourse analysis (CDA) of included documents. CDA aims to uncover and understand the implicit and explicit power dynamics employed in discourses by examining hidden meanings, ideologies, preconceived ideas, values, and positionalities (Cummings et al., 2020). CDA studies the discursive strategies of dominance and resistance that are present in social structures, including those related to class, race, ethnicity, gender, ability, and age, as reflected in texts such as policies and codes of conduct (Amri et al., 2025; Cummings et al., 2020). This approach is highly relevant for exploring research fairness, since it enables us to see how the concept is constructed, reinforced, or resisted in RI discourses. In this way, using CDA for qualitative analysis is not theoretically neutral but rather requires taking a critical - and in our case, anti-imperialist, anti-colonial – stance (Cummings et al., 2020).

As a first step in our analysis, we inductively coded the retrieved documents with regard to how they addressed fairness (implicitly or explicitly). We adopted a critical stance, being attentive to silences, nuances, power dynamics and how language was employed in the discourses. Following this, we identified independent constructing blocks on the concept of fairness, both inductively and deductively. The inductive blocks were identified by paying attention to latent ideas and perspectives linked to the concept of fairness as repeated in the data. The deductive constructing blocks were theoretically informed based on the themes discussed in Table 1, namely 1) fairness as addressing injustices, 2) fairness as attention to colonial hierarchies and 3) fairness as DEI. Both material aligning with or building on the deductive blocks, as well as challenging them, were included in the analysis. Finally, we compared representations of fairness across documents. This helped us to understand how different texts construct the concept, showing hidden assumptions and variations in its meaning.

The first 12 documents were independently coded by CPP and KL using MAXQDA. Few discrepancies in the coding were found, and were resolved through discussion. Following this, the rest of the documents were coded by CPP or KL. After the first full analysis, CPP checked all coded documents again to ensure consistency, and re-coded previous documents with any newly developed inductive codes. Meetings with all authors were held to discuss the coding tree and iteratively refine the codebook.

Themes were developed based on the previously identified constructing blocks (Table 3), as well as inductive blocks that emerged from the data. During the development of the themes, the alignment between codes and themes across all documents was checked to ensure systematic coverage and coherence of the coding tree. When overlaps or redundancies were detected, codes were reorganized to refine the thematic structure and ensure that each theme captured a different aspect of fairness.

Results

Distribution of documents

The results of the RI documents search are presented in a PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1). A total of 65 documents were included, with details on each available in the [supplementary information 3](#). The included documents come from 39 countries, with a major representation of national documents from European (24) countries. The included documents provide limited representation from African (2), Latin American (1) and North American (1), countries and comparatively higher representation from Asian (9) and Oceania (2) countries. Figure 2 presents an overview of the countries for which national or within-country RI guidelines were found, while Figure 3 shows regions covered by documents that apply to multiple countries within the same geographic area.

Figure 1: PRISMA flowchart of the included documents

*Using AI screening tool Rayyan (<https://new.rayyan.ai/>).

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Figure 2: Countries covered by national RI guidelines and policies

Figure 3: Countries covered by regional RI guidelines and policies

How the documents address fairness

A total of 5 themes were identified from the inductive-deductive analysis of the 65 included documents. Theme 1 focuses on the different guiding principles to RI found across the documents as well as on the diversity in the goals of research. Themes 2 to 5 represent four different approaches to fairness found in the documents. The themes are described below. The codes' frequency table is presented in the [supplementary information 4](#). The numbers in parentheses in the sections below refer to specific guidelines, as referred to in the [supplementary information 3](#).

Theme 1: Guiding principles of RI and research goals

In most documents, the definition and conceptualization of these terms is expressed in the articulation of moral principles or research processes and regulations (Table 4).

Table 4: Crucial aspects of RI explicitly mentioned and conceptualized across documents

	Crucial aspects of RI	What is included in the group (explicit terms mentioned in the documents)?	Number of documents and percentage	Example(s)
1	Being a good person / researcher	good will, responsibility, accountability, respect and care for participants, confidentiality, dignity of participants, obligations, informed consent	50 (77%)	“Researchers should take full responsibility for the consequences of their research in regard to themselves, research subjects, or society at large.” (D44)
2	Openness	transparency, openness, honesty, disclosure, sincerity, availability and accessibility of results/data/analysis, traceability, open access, candor	49 (75%)	“Transparency means, among other things, ensuring that it is clear to others what data the research was based on, how the data were obtained, what and how results were achieved and what role was played by external stakeholders. If parts of the research or data are not to be made public, the researcher must provide a good account of why this is not possible.” (D01)
3	Objectivity and meticulousness	impartiality, accuracy, objectivity, truth, veracity, reproducibility, replicability, rigour, reliability, truthfulness, meticulousness, scrupulousness	46 (71%)	“(iii) Objectivity in collecting and handling data and information, presenting evidence and findings, and interpreting results. (iv) Impartiality in conducting research, communicating, and judging the contributions of others.” (D60)
4	Freedom	independence, academic freedom, freedom of intellect, freedom of expression, (self) criticism, free inquiry	38 (58%)	“Academic freedom. Research institutions shall assist in ensuring the researchers’ freedom in their choice of topic and methodology, implementation of research and publication of results.” (D49) “Freedom means that the researcher is free to choose the research problem or hypothesis; is free to search for new research ideas and critically assess the existing ones; is free to choose the research group, research institution or sources of financing.” (D55)
5	Research processes	conflicts of interest, documentation, authorship, publication,	38 (58%)	“Only those who have made a substantial contribution to the research, analysis, and interpretation of results

		data management, review		may be listed as authors of scientific reports and publications. Contributions such as consultation, comments, or technical and editorial support should be acknowledged but do not warrant co-authorship. The order of authorship is mutually agreed upon by co-authors.” (D32)
6	Laws and rules	binding laws, legal system, policies, regulations, guidelines, institutional agreements	34 (52)	“Laws and regulations. In the field of research, there are national laws and regulations as well as applicable international conventions and agreements, and researchers and research institutions must abide by these.” (D49)
7	Collegiality and cooperation	collegiality, cooperation, collaborations, treatment between researchers, junior researchers, reciprocity, exchange, good manners	31 (48%)	“Reciprocity and cooperation with others in the performance of one’s duties” (D53) “Special consideration of the needs of young researchers; Education and the development of proper attitudes among young scientists constitutes a particularly important element of the system. The institutions should specify relevant rights of the "masters" and rules of responsibility for educating young scientists in their internal by-laws and should make sure that they are abided by. Particular attention should be paid to the responsibility of PH.D., M.Sc. and licentiate promoters. Every member of a research team must have a senior, experienced partner responsible for the trainee's scientific development.” (D52)
8	Social and environmental concerns	social value, public engagement, wellbeing of society, effective managing of natural resources, social commitment, communication to society, common good, sustainability, dual use, social interests, social responsibility and impact	32 (49%)	“Researchers should be committed to undertaking academic research which is in the interests of social well-being. They should avoid having anything to do with research which is potentially subversive or which is against moral values traditionally upheld by society.” (D44) “She/he should abstain from participating in projects that constitute potential harm to humanity, the environment and biodiversity and/or targets modern media and communication” (D31)
9	Fairness	fairness, equality, diversity, inclusion, justice,	28 (43%)	“Diversity is not simply the representation of individuals and ideas

		awareness on social biases, unconscious social biases, discrimination		but is actual inclusion, which can only be achieved by creating a culture of openness, and recognizing and addressing unconscious bias.” (D61) “Fairness means treating other researchers fairly and with respect throughout the entire research process. Fairness towards other researchers is especially important in the review processes and in the investigation of research misconduct.” (D17)
10	Reputation	reputation, credibility, standards of institutions, trust, trustworthiness, reputation, quality, excellence, competency, qualification	30 (46%)	“The scientific researcher or research institution aims to achieve a high level of research and ensure the high-quality dissemination of its results.” (D19) “The application of principles and values, and the respect for deontology and standards of professional ethics guarantee the quality of research and enhance the reputation and public image of science, greatly contributing to its advancements and to progress in society.” (D53)
11	Balance	correction, moderation, correctness, efficiency, diligence, discipline, harmony	15 (23%)	“Scientific autonomy brings with it great responsibility and an obligation to self-observe, self-regulate and act with integrity at all times.” (D42) “ <i>mana</i> means balancing one's own authority and the rights held by others;” (D27)

Additional to the different framings of RI, the framing of research also varies across the included documents. In many cases, research is portrayed as inherently good or beneficial, with little critical reflection on its potential harms or limitations. Several codes adopt a neoliberal framing of research, emphasizing research as a market asset tied to productivity, innovation and economic growth. Others present research as a driver for social progress, reinforcing the instrumentalist and positive narrative of research and science. In contrast, there are fewer documents that frame research as a powerful tool to understand the world, or which acknowledge that research benefits are closely tied to the care, responsibility and ethical awareness with which research is conducted.

Theme 2: Fairness as addressing systemic injustices

This theme concerns whether, and if so how, the documents address injustices in research. This theme includes three subthemes: 1) injustices related to colonial history, 2) socioeconomic injustices, and 3) injustices affecting the environment. GN documents often fail to acknowledge these three forms of systemic injustice in a meaningful way. Many entirely neglect these issues, while the vast majority might

do lip service to the issues but offer little to no guidance on how such injustices could be addressed or challenged.

2.1. Injustices related to colonial history

There are no documents that explicitly mention 'colonialism'. A small number of them discuss inequities in knowledge production in different countries, although not referring to these as colonial legacies or realities. For instance, the Best Practice Guide for Research Integrity and Ethics (Document (D) 17) from Austria pays attention to GN exploitation of the Global South (GS) in research, stressing that this type of exploitation goes against the principles of RI and research ethics (RE).

“Ethics dumping ... is the case if unethical research practices from a high-income environment are exported to a resource-poor environment. This concerns, on the one hand, deliberate exploitation, for instance, if researchers carry out their work in resource-poor countries because the research work is forbidden in their own environment. On the other hand, there is exploitation due to inadequate knowledge or insufficient ethical awareness. A lack of appropriate oversight mechanisms on site can further exacerbate the problem.” (D17, p. 16)

Like in this example, in the documents which address international collaborations, developmentalist language – for instance reflected in the choice of words of “resource-poor countries” or “lower-capacity parties” to denominate the GS – still reinforces colonial hierarchies by portraying former colonies as lacking and former colonial powers as leading, while simultaneously not addressing the roots behind differences in wealth.

An aspect of colonial injustices found in some of the included documents is a prompt and active call for protection from external extractivist logics and undue foreign influences. This is present in documents with diverse origins, such as from The Code of Ethics for Researchers from The Czech Academy of Sciences (D10) and the San Code of Conduct of Research Ethics (D34), written by indigenous peoples in Southern Africa. For instance, the Czech code states that:

“[Research ethics]...strives to strengthen the institutional resilience of the Czech Academy of Sciences and does not consciously create space for unwanted influence of a foreign power.” (D10, para. 28)

2.2. Socioeconomic injustices

Some documents recognize the socioeconomic dimension of research and emphasize the importance of support structures that enable participation from individuals across different social and economic backgrounds (D10, D25, D48). Other documents, such as the Code of Ethics for Research Workers from Poland (D38), even go one step further, adopting a systemic perspective that criticizes the increasing commercialization of research:

“Changing external and internal circumstances, such as the massification of higher education, increasing number of researchers, the need to apply for research funding, parametric assessment of researchers and scientific institutions and conflicts of interest associated with the commercialisation of research results, all these prompt us to pay special attention to the intensifying in recent years phenomena such as courtesy reviews, plagiarism, multiple-job holding

(moonlighting), unjustified citing of works, using institutional resources for one's own personal benefit." (D38, p. 3)

The Taiwan Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (D63) describes the context of growing inequality within the national knowledge economy, and how market demands from the private sector can exacerbate social injustice:

"Taiwan is a high-tech "knowledge society," in which the socio-economic gap between the rich and the poor is expanding. Rather than a gradual evolution, this expansion has occurred suddenly and quickly, leaving little time for the society to adapt. Profit-oriented high-tech companies often demand immediate short-term gains without paying attention to emerging inequities, social injustice and long-term effects." (D63, p 19)

2.3. Injustices affecting the environment

We placed concerns about environmental issues under systemic injustice, since climate change and ecological degradation disproportionately impact the countries that have contributed the least to causing these problems, exposing a profound global and systemic injustice. A majority of the documents mention sustainability or environmental issues. In most of these cases, environmental sustainability is framed as part of researchers' responsibilities, specifically in terms of protection of, and respect and care for the environment. However, these codes rarely describe what such care entails or how researchers should act to protect the natural environment. Only a few documents provide more specific examples and explicitly connect natural elements and environments protection to local communities and cultural heritage, such as the example below from the Estonian Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Agreement (D54):

"2.3.5 The researcher respects the integrity of natural environment and spiritual and material heritage, and removes objects under study from their original environment only in substantiated cases.

2.3.6 The researcher avoids damaging the natural environment and cultural heritage. If endangered species, protected monuments or areas are studied, the researcher applies for the necessary permits and coordinations." (D54, p.10)

Only a few documents mention climate change; those that do link it to the responsibilities of researchers. A case of that is the Code of Ethics for Researchers of the Czech Academy of Sciences (D10), which states:

"...does not waste material and energy resources, strives to reduce the climate and environmental footprint of his/her activities" (D10, para. 27)

Theme 3: Fairness as attention to knowledge hierarchies

This theme illustrates how the included documents address knowledge hierarchies related to 1) epistemic hierarchies and 2) hierarchies in ethical frameworks.

3.1. Epistemic hierarchies

This theme addresses assumptions about whose voices are taken seriously in producing knowledge, and who is considered an active agent of research, as well as which knowledge systems are considered as academically valid.

3.1.2. Hierarchies in knowledge agents

Most documents reflect hierarchical representations of agents of research through the tone, words, and language used, often either implicitly or explicitly portraying structurally marginalized groups as vulnerable subjects, rather than as knowledge producers. This reduces research relationships as a dichotomy of active-passive agents in research, framing marginalized groups as passive receivers of research that, in most of the occasions, need external protection or guidance to do research. This 'othering' portrays marginalized groups as lacking agency and reinforces power imbalances. With their choice of words, these documents present researchers as the "we", without reflecting on what this "we" looks like, but implicitly assuming that this plural first-person subject, capable of doing and leading research as a valid knowledge creator, cannot be part of marginalized populations. Examples of this dichotomy can be found in *The TRUST Code: A Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships* (D39):

Researchers from high-income settings need to be aware of the power and resource differentials in benefit-sharing discussions, with sustained efforts to bring lower-capacity parties into the dialogue (D39, p. 2)

Lower educational standards, illiteracy or language barriers can never be an excuse for hiding information or providing it incompletely. (D39, p. 3)

Here, the distinction between a "we", portraying a GN researcher that leads research in the GS and the "other", portraying a GS research team that accepts and facilitates such research is enforced by word choice. The existence of a "lower-capacity" receiving party ("other") or "lower educational standards" presupposes the existence of a higher-capacity party that also has higher educational standards, in this case exporter of tools and experience in doing research ("we"). While in this example, there is an intention of addressing and improving how research treats and engages with indigenous populations or with parties from the GS, it still assumes a dichotomy between the active, leading researcher and the recipient in need of guidance and 'capacity' building, reinforcing colonial hierarchies. In the following quote, exemptions to inclusion of local communities are also explicitly allowed:

Local communities and research participants should be included throughout the research process, wherever possible, from planning through to post-study feedback and evaluation, to ensure that their perspectives are fairly represented (D39, p. 2)

The possibility to exclude local communities from research done on them again reinforces colonial hierarchies by placing the power of deciding when inclusion or exclusion is ethical at the hands of GN actors.

Another example relating to hierarchies in knowledge agents can be found in the *South Africa National Research Foundation Statement on Ethical Research and Scholarly Publishing Practices* (D66), in which indigenous populations and their knowledge are portrayed as valuable and, as such, should be acknowledged. However, the requirements for authorship are less clear and state that those who made a material contribution to the research or publication might still not meet authorship criteria (p. 1), without clearly specifying what constitutes a material contribution.

In contrast, a smaller number of documents defy, and break, the “we” versus “other” dichotomy by framing structurally marginalized groups as active knowers and research agents. These include documents written by members of Indigenous communities, such as the Te Ara Tika Guidelines for Māori research ethics: A framework for researchers and ethics committee members (D57) and the San Code of Research Ethics (D34). The choice of words, in these cases, differs from the previously mentioned documents. Specifically, this can be seen in the use of first-person grammatical verbs in document the San Code of Research Ethics (D34) or in the inclusion of Māori language as a substantial part of the text the Te Ara Tika Guidelines (D57).

The San Code of Conduct (D34) highlights that for research to be ethical, it should follow the San protocols, principles and processes. It also states that the San people should not be seen as subjects of research, but rather as active agents of any research conducted about them, and therefore should be acknowledged and respected as research contributors:

Respect requires that our contribution to research is acknowledged at all times. (D34, p. 2)

It is important that the San be meaningfully involved in the proposed studies, which includes learning about the benefits that the participants and the community might expect. These might be largely non-monetary but include co-research opportunities, sharing of skills and research capacity, and roles for translators and research assistants, to give some examples. (D34, p. 3)

In the case of the Te Ara Tika Guidelines for Māori Ethics (D57), the document does not only provide guidelines that protect Māori people in research, but brings Māori people to the center of research, breaking the dichotomy between “researcher = non-indigenous” and “research subject = indigenous” that is often present in settler-colonial states. Furthermore, it also establishes that research should be Māori-led in its totality:

This approach to the research design acknowledges the importance of partnerships and the responsibilities of Māori to ensuring the project delivers its intended outcomes to Māori communities. Use of a kaupapa Māori framework to develop research that is designed by, conducted by, made up of, and benefits, Māori is promoted. We encourage research that frames Māori kaupapa as the primary interest of the project, involves Māori as co-constructors of the project, supports kaupapa Māori theory and uses Māori research methodologies as appropriate. (D57, p. 16)

3.1.3. Hierarchies in knowledge systems

Only a minority of the documents acknowledge the validity of diverse epistemic values and systems, with most instead promoting GN knowledge systems. In general, many of the included documents frame ‘objectivity’ as *the* approach of scientific research; this implicitly excludes diverse epistemic values. Furthermore, in many of the included documents, objectivity is also associated with statistical analysis and quantitative methodologies, which can exclude qualitative methodologies used in a broad range of disciplines including the humanities, linguistics, social sciences but also health-related research, environmental research, etc. This is highlighted by the language, and the associated scientific paradigms, reflected in the documents, e.g. “replicability”, “systematic investigation”, “applied sciences”, “empirical research”, “laboratory”, among others. An example of that can be found in the CSIC Code of Good Scientific Practices of Spain (D41):

Science is based on empiricism and logical reasoning. Observation and experimentation in the laboratory or in the natural environment are aimed at obtaining data that will provide suitable answers to the scientific questions posed. For this reason, research must be carried out according to well-designed and well-defined working protocols, which can be analysed and interpreted by any researcher in the scientific field in question. (D41, p. 38)

There are some documents that acknowledge diverse knowledge systems and epistemic values. In general, these documents come from countries and regions that have suffered colonization or whose indigenous populations have been oppressed and marginalized. However, the degree to which these diverse knowledge systems are central to these documents varies. While in some documents (D36, D62) it is stated that indigenous knowledge should be respected, in others indigenous knowledge and diverse epistemologies are framed as essential parts of research. An example of the latter is the Code of Professional Standards and Ethics in Science, Technology, and the Humanities of New Zealand (D35):

This Code applies across all fields of science, technology and the humanities, and across differing knowledge systems and research epistemologies, so as to address the complexity of ethical and practice concerns that may arise in Members' work. (D35, p.1)

3.2. Hierarchies in ethical frameworks

Hierarchies relating to ethical frameworks can also be found in the included documents. Here we differentiate between GS documents that adopt or closely follow guidance documents developed in the GN, often without adaptation to local cultural or ethical contexts, from documents that incorporate diverse ethical traditions, acknowledging the legitimacy of diverse principles and values.

There is an implicit, in some cases very subtle, aspirational tone in documents coming from countries that are less represented in research outputs. This is reflected in these documents modeling, "copying", paraphrasing or taking as references well-established GN documents such as The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity or The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – documents that are referenced in more than 60% of the included documents –. The scope of this modeling includes references to specific principles, descriptions of acceptable and unacceptable practices, and even the full structures of these documents. The dominance of Global North standards and norms is also reflected in the way some documents from the GS articulate aspirations to become "civilised" (D52), "developed" (D33), "modern" (D31) through establishing RI guidelines or wanting to be more aligned with GN research standards. These aspirations are expressed both explicitly and implicitly, often positioning GN countries as models to imitate.

There are also examples of framing ethical diversity in a negative way. In The APEC Guiding Principles for Research Integrity (D36), the cultural differences across Asian Pacific economies are acknowledged but, at the same time, the variety of shared principles is seen as a barrier for research:

There are cultural differences across APEC economies and varying approaches towards undertaking research in each of these economies. Research is increasingly an international activity, with collaborative exchanges becoming more commonplace. Research practices that prioritise integrity are essential as these activities expand on a global scale. The absence of a shared set of principles for research integrity is seen as a barrier to increased researcher mobility and collaboration between researchers in APEC economies. (D36, p. 4)

Few documents advocate for diversity in ethical frameworks. The documents that do so discuss research that involves international collaborations or come from countries or regions that have suffered colonisation. In the first case, examples can be found in the UKRI Code of Practice for Research (D3), which while discussing international research collaborations, takes into account that ethical standards might be different in different countries and requires researchers to be aware of those:

Will your research comply with all legal (including health and safety) and ethical requirements and other applicable guidelines, including those from other organisations and/or countries, if relevant? (D3, p.7)

Only two documents (D35, D57), both from New Zealand, address indigenous ethical frameworks. D35, the Code of Professional Standards and Ethics in Science, Technology, and the Humanities, is a bi-cultural document, embracing Maori ethical frameworks in combination with GN frameworks without establishing a hierarchy and providing a narrative explanation of the connections between these and acknowledging that their use depends on the context of research:

The Code prioritises neither the established [GN] research ethics principles nor the Māori values, and encourages Members to regard them as working together to guide action appropriate to their specific research context: Tika Mana, Whakapapa, Manaakitanga, Pūkenga, Kaitiakitanga, Justice, Duty of care, Beneficence, Non-maleficence, Respect, Integrity (D35, p. 2)

This code, with its word choices, indicates that the “established” ethics principles are the GN ones, being one of the only examples that actually makes this spread of GN frameworks explicit, while also providing specific guidance on how to apply different ethical frameworks in research practices.

On the other hand, D57 includes a Māori ethical framework only, which is in line with the target group of the document, which is directed to: “those who engage in consultation or advice about Māori ethical issues from a local, regional, national or international perspective (D57, p. 7)”.

Theme 4: Fairness as equity, diversity and inclusion

The terms “equity”, “diversity” and “inclusion” appear in a large number of the included documents, with at least one of these words being mentioned in less than half of the documents. However, their uses vary significantly in terms of depth and meaning. Some engage with these terms in a meaningful way, proposing specific actions to promote inclusive practices in research and to address structural inequalities, including race and gender-based discrimination and harassment. Among these documents, inclusion is portrayed as a tool to make research more democratic and accessible to all social groups, within and outside academia. In the case of inside academia, some documents present a positive view of inclusion and diversity, framing these as enriching research. For instance, this is observable in the National Policy of on Academic Ethics of India (D27):

Academic communities are enriched by the presence of people of different ethnicities, genders, religions, castes, tribes, socioeconomic strata, affiliations, backgrounds and sexual orientations. There must be no direct or indirect bias or discrimination against any individual based on the above categories. Members should pro-actively strive to improve the balance of under-represented sections. (D27, p. 3)

Some documents highlight the importance of including agents outside academia in order to increase the acceptance and relevance of research for society and promote different strategies to do so, such as participatory action research, citizen science and consultations processes, advocating that the participation of these actors in research should not be limited to dissemination of results. A good example of this is the Best Practice Guide for Research Integrity and Ethics (D17) from Austria:

The involvement of society should not begin with the communication of results but should take place earlier in the research process, in a form appropriate to the particular topic. As such, public involvement in research would not be regarded as merely the “extra credit work” of individual researchers but as something that requires institutional support and recognition. (D17, p. 32)

Additionally, some documents embrace inclusive language within their own writing. Examples include gender-inclusive terminology and embedding marginalized languages in texts written in English by offering in-text translations, such as the Te Ara Tika Guidelines for Māori research ethics (D57), which gives Māori language a central role in the document. While it is true that some documents are sensitive to gender including both the masculine and feminine pronouns (he/she) when talking about researchers, these take a binary approach to gender, excluding gender-non-conforming identities.

Of the documents that explicitly address inequities in research, most focus on the dimension of gender rather than other identity characteristics, and promote ‘equality of opportunities’ rather than equity. For instance the Austrian Best Practice Guide for Research Integrity and Ethics (D17):

“Currently, career opportunities for men and women are still unequal in science and research. According to the SHE Figures Report of the European Commission, women in Europe face greater difficulties than men in advancing to the highest academic positions. According to this report, Austria also still lags behind in the share of female researchers compared to the EU average. One reason for this is that the hiring and promotion decisions are sometimes based on subtle practices of institutional discrimination: seemingly neutral rules and criteria which have different impacts on different groups are used to maintain the existing (gender) ratios. Although research excellence is touted publicly as the deciding factor, certain biases in the evaluation practices can disadvantage women and other groups in science and research.” (D17, p. 33)

In some documents, gender-based misconduct, including sexual harassment, is presented as a central barrier to women’s participation in academia, as can be seen in the National Policy of on Academic Ethics of India (D27):

Sexual misconduct and/or gender-based harassment in the workplace are totally unacceptable. Legal structures and rules regarding how to deal with sexual misconduct must be rigorously followed. There also exist many forms of behavior which may not amount to harassment in the legal sense but constitute gender-based discrimination. Institutions should strive to ensure that their members do not engage in such actions and should pro-actively sensitize their community on these issues. (D27, p. 3)

More than a half of the documents either do not mention DEI, or approach these in a more symbolic or superficial way, reflecting a more tokenistic or performative vision. In these cases, the word “diversity” often appears without further elaboration, concrete actions, or clear links to research practices. In some documents, diversity is linked to other values, such as respect (D1, D23, D42). While these documents

make a connection between diversity and research integrity or responsible conduct of research, their framing of what diversity in academia means is vague, as can be seen in the example below, from the Code of Conduct for Scientific Integrity from Switzerland (D42):

RESPECT for colleagues, students, study and research participants, society, our cultural heritage, ecosystems and the environment. Due consideration should be given to the diversity and life experience of all persons involved. (D42, p. 16)

Theme 5: Procedural fairness

Many documents use the term “fairness” to refer to procedural fairness, aimed at promoting fairness or rigor in the way that certain processes are implemented in research environments. Most of the included documents make use of the adjective “fair” when providing guidance on authorship, feedback, recognition, evaluation or dissemination. In some of these cases, while procedural fairness is highly relevant for research integrity, the use of the word fairness sometimes appears as superficial and critically underdeveloped. Concepts like “fair authorship”, “fair feedback”, “fair dissemination” or “fair evaluation” are mentioned in most of the documents, but it is less common that the codes provide explanation of what they exactly mean. In some codes, fairness in research processes is equal to rigor, transparency, objectiveness and respect, emphasizing process integrity (including exception of biases) but without mentioning power dynamics, for instance as stated in the Code of Conduct for Responsible Research from China (D56):

Objective, Fair, and Rigorous Review: Reviewers should conduct evaluations in an objective, fair, and rigorous manner, respecting the dignity and academic autonomy of the authors being reviewed. They should acknowledge diverse academic viewpoints and provide constructive feedback and suggestions. Review comments should not include insulting, degrading, or unfair remarks. Evaluations should not be influenced by non-academic factors. (D56, para. 102)

Another important dimension of procedural fairness addressed in some documents is the respect and protection of researchers. Here, fairness is linked to ensuring safe, ethical, and just working conditions. Mental health, in this framing, becomes an issue of fairness in how research environments and processes are structured and managed, as stated in the UKRI Code of Practice for Research (D3):

Avoid unrealistic demands that increase workload but decrease productivity. Time pressure and workload issues have a significant impact on good research culture and can open the door to questionable research practices that may lead to research misconduct. (D3, p. 32)

Discussion

In this scoping review, we have shown that a majority of national and international RI guidelines originate from Europe. Many of the guidelines either do not address questions of fairness (including diversity, equity, inclusion, justice and equality) or do so superficially. In fact, fairness is often only mentioned in relation to procedural integrity of processes to be conducted in the research environment such as authorship and peer review. Few guidelines actually address systematic injustices such as colonial and socio-economic inequities, whereas those which do attempt to address equitable collaborations and protection of vulnerable participants and communities run the risk of reproducing inequitable dynamics by

implicitly assuming that active knowledge producers are from the GN, while others are framed as “lower-capacity parties” recipients of the results of research. Finally, while some documents address DEI, most only focus on a binary understanding of gender and do not provide a clear rationale of why DEI is needed in research. All in all, this shows that fairness is not a central or serious concern in current RI guidelines across the world.

Our findings resonate with a pattern that Israel (2018), Schrag (2010), Tealdi (2006), and Macklin (1999), among others already identified in RE governance, and which they referred to as ethical or moral imperialism. Ethical imperialism refers to the practice of exporting moral values and research ethics practices and governance between disciplines – from the biomedical disciplines to social sciences according to Schrag (2010) – and countries – from the GN to the GS according to Israel (2018) and Tealdi (2006). This pattern, until now mostly identified in RE, is also present in RI governance as shown in this scoping review both in the unequal geographical distribution of the included documents as well as in their content. Overall, most included documents come from GN regions, mostly European countries, with fewer coming from Asia and with very limited representation from Africa and Latin America². This unequal distribution shows that these frameworks are the most available and, therefore, disproportionately influence and shape the international academic discourse on RI. Regarding the content of the documents, this influence becomes even clearer: GN values and frameworks are spread through the replication of existing codes, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, which are either copied or referenced in other national guidelines, also outside of Europe, in many occasions without substantial local adaptation. Furthermore, many codes described as “international” and developed to be applied globally are written mostly by GN institutions or authors.

Different factors might explain why there is a pattern of ethical imperialism in RI guidance documents for researchers. First, the structures of powerful publishers and funders create strong incentives for GS institutions to adopt or develop codes that align, refer to and are based on GN standards and codes. Thus, GS institutions might see this replication of European codes as a strategic and crucial decision to increase their chances of funding and expanding international legitimacy. Second, colonial legacies and ongoing forms of colonialism have led to an unequal distribution of economic resources for GS countries to independently develop, publish, and disseminate research as well as RI structures and governance, including national codes (Bhambra, 2018). Even more likely, in some contexts, questions of integrity and ethics in research might be addressed through other forms of regulation that escape the ethical frameworks and epistemic structures imposed from the GN, for instance, through more community-led initiatives. These might not resemble GN institutionalized RI initiatives and practices that, in many cases, equalize moral thought and reflection to bureaucratic processes or might not use the GN imposed formats and modes of dissemination (Tuhiwai Smith, 2012) and therefore remain invisible in international discourses.

The included documents also show an epistemic dominance of GN epistemic values and frameworks. A distinction of the included RI documents is that they tend to promote and center objectivity as a defining trait of research legitimacy and, with that, reinforce Eurocentric epistemic values. In most RI documents, epistemic traits such as objectivity, are framed as if they were timeless and universal. Scholars like Quijano (2000) or Tuhiwai Smith (2012), have critiqued how knowledge systems themselves are shaped by colonial legacies and how this is always obscured in academic spaces and publications. Stone-

² While the US is not represented in our included documents, probably due to not having one national RI code of conduct and basing its RI governance either in legal documents or in institutional guidelines – which are excluded in this study according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria – , authors with US affiliations appear as contributors or advisors to several codes included in this scoping review.

Mediatore (2018) specifically describes how objectivity has been presented as a timeless and universal value of knowledge promoted from former European empires, but in fact emerged from, and was reinforced by, the hierarchies of industrial capitalism and colonial modernity. This epistemic model continues to shape research by framing what is presented as “objective” as universal and therefore legitimate, while dismissing other situated knowledges and procedures that do not fit in the “rigorousness” of the first as “subjective” and not considered as valid forms of knowledge.

By reproducing this dichotomy, the majority of RI documents establish an objectivity-guided and universal *Us*. This *Us* belongs to the GN, imposing its own knowledge systems since only it is seen as having the ability to conduct research and create knowledge. This *Us* can be contrasted with an inevitable subjectivity-guided, local, ‘lower capacity’ *Other* – a GS one, which is not capable of producing knowledge but needs support and help from the *Us*. The *Other* is either explicitly or implicitly treated as someone whose knowledge needs to be validated by the *Us* in order to be legitimized and become credible. This corresponds to what Fricker defined as testimonial epistemic injustice (2007): the moral wrongs enacted against structurally marginalized groups in their capacity as knowers through being given less credibility. It also resonates with critiques of Fricker, such as Dotson’s (2012) account of contributory epistemic injustice, which occurs when structurally marginalized groups are able to generate and communicate knowledge, but their contributions are not recognized because audiences have their own interpretive frameworks that are themselves biased.

Moreover, RI discourses often replicate asymmetries in ethical frameworks. While there are historical contextualizations of research ethics and integrity in some of the included documents, they normally begin after the Second World War, leaving out colonial histories and the moral implications of transatlantic imperialism (Bhambra, 2018) omitting the influence of these in current research practices. Even in those documents aimed at types of research in which the hierarchies and legacies of colonization are present and vivid – such as codes of conduct aiming to guide international collaborations between the GS and GN –, these major historical injustices and even its vocabulary are absolutely neglected: the word *colonization* is not present in any of the included documents. This omission was already identified and described by Bhambra (2007) as a consequence of this same coloniality: it is the result of European colonialism what elides colonialism in its own discourses and knowledge and naturalizes Eurocentric epistemic and moral frameworks as universally valid. Again, in this framing, the GN becomes the implicit standard of moral practice, while the GS becomes the *Other*, consisting of sites of intervention, or objects of protection rather than full moral agents.

These dynamics of othering are not incidental. They show how RI discourses, by neglecting history, political contexts and colonial hierarchies, silently reinforce imaginaries of superiority and inferiority: what is “good” versus “bad” research, which ethics are “valid” versus which are “not enough”, which voices can be legitimated and which cannot. The consequence of these silences and alienation to history in RI documents is that the possibilities for genuinely having alternative epistemic ethical imaginaries are very limited. Any action towards inclusion, even if well-intentioned, risks falling into tokenism if it is not rooted and situated historically and politically. This also highlights the need for former colonial countries to be accountable for how their research practices have harmed and continue to harm others. Scholars such as Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2018) or Tuhiwai Smith (2012) have exposed how colonial knowledge systems not only dismiss, but actively damage GS and Indigenous communities, and their knowledge systems. This means that RI in the GN should acknowledge plural and situated approaches of research, and should explicitly acknowledge their own historical and political positioning, the harms they contribute to research and the benefits they obtain from that harm, as part of defining their RI standards.

Furthermore, anticolonial scholars have argued for plural and situated frameworks that recognize GS and Indigenous populations as equally valid sources of knowledge and ethical frameworks (Dutta et al., 2021; Tuhiwai Smith, 2012). In fact, good examples are already included in this review. The *Guidelines for Māori research ethics: A framework for researchers and ethics committee members* (Document 57) or the *San Code on Research Ethics* (Document 34), show that it is possible to explicitly integrate GS and Indigenous knowledge and ethical frameworks in RI guiding documents for researchers in a situated way. These can serve as ways to move beyond tokenistic references to diversity to actually recognize and integrate alternative epistemologies and ethical frameworks as well as address the GN's silences on their imperial, colonizer pasts and presents.

This study provides the first systematic scoping review of RI documents critically assessing the treatment of fairness. Moreover, it is also the first one that takes an explicit anticolonial and systemic justice perspective, putting structural inequalities in the center of the analysis. Its strength lies in uncovering silences and implicit assumptions that shape how fairness is understood globally. However, this scoping review also has some limitations: first, we focused on national and international guidance and might have missed important institutional guidelines and, consequently, missed to include countries that rely on institutional guidelines for RI or laws (e.g. the USA). Second, despite efforts to include non-English sources and direct contact with experts in all countries and nations, we may have missed some documents due to language restrictions. Fourth, translations were done using AI tools, including ChatGPT or DeepSeek which might have biases or mistakes we were unable to identify for all languages. Finally, because our search relied on Eurocentric channels of distribution, it is possible that we missed documents that circulate using other pathways.

Conclusion

Our study demonstrates that while fairness is frequently mentioned in RI codes, it is rarely treated as a structural principle connected to justice. Instead, fairness is often reduced to procedural compliance or has vague references to diversity and tokenistic inclusion, completing neglecting the complicity and contribution of academia to violence and inequity in the world. By failing to situate research in its historical, political and social contexts, most of the included documents end up reproducing colonial hierarchies of both knowledge and ethical frameworks. However, a small number of documents, particularly those developed by Indigenous or GS populations or communities, offer hopeful alternatives, portraying research as situated, offering diverse epistemic and ethical frameworks and framing fairness as resistance and protection to oppression. These examples suggest that it is possible to move from a socially and historically alienated account of RI toward a more inclusive, justice-oriented, and transformative vision of research integrity.

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